

Skewed Spatial Dynamic Probability in Quantum Mechanics

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In previous notes, we argued that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, allows for x,t and $x+hbar/p$, $t+hbar/p$ solutions. We suggested this might give rise to the quantum mechanical probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In other notes, we sought a probability which conserves energy and momentum and respects Lorentz invariance, again leading to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In a couple of notes, we argued that the uncertainty in x arises from a rest mass at $x=0$ jumping to $x'/t' = v$ as seen in the moving frame. This uncertainty in x forces one to introduce probabilities.

Here we combine the latter idea with the notion that special relativity yields formulas for the interaction variables E and p . We argue that one may replace the notion of a force reaction as well as the idea of frames moving at constant speed relative to each other by demanding that an interaction be represented by an AND (product) of probabilities and this must necessarily conserve energy and momentum. This probability is in the location and time of interactions.

This leads to a skewed dynamic probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ because $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are not the same. Furthermore, as we have noted before, one uses $\exp(ipx)$ as an interaction probability which leads to complex average kinetic energy (nonrelativistic case) and momentum if one only uses $p \geq 0$. The Schrodinger equation (which is based on conservation of energy) bypasses this problem by combining $p \geq 0$ and $p < 0$. Nevertheless, we note that there can exist $W(x) = \sum_{p>0} a(p)\exp(ipx)$ such that if $W(x) = 0$ dW/dx and $d/dx dW/dx$ are also zero at these points even though the average kinetic energy and momentum are complex.

We finally show that a complex average can be used in a physical calculation, namely one dimensional reflection-refraction.

Newtonian $x=vt$ and Special Relativity

A free particle travels according to: $x = vt$ ((1)) where $v = \text{constant}$

dx and dt represent intervals along the path and there is no notion of interaction nor interaction variables. ((1)) may be used to develop special relativity which introduces exact formulas for E and p , i.e.

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((2))$$

Furthermore, it yields the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + px$ ((3))

((3)) is understood to use x, t such that $x = vt$. If one, however, uses dx and dt in ((3)) and sets it to 0, then

$$dx = hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad dt = hbar/E \quad ((4))$$

dx and dt in ((4)) cannot be the dx and dt values used in ((1)). Furthermore, they are associated with E and p and so in previous notes, we argued that dx and dt are intervals of uncertain interaction hits in t and x . This leads to the notion of a probability

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((5))$$

An alternative approach to obtaining ((5)), which we have presented before, is to seek a probability which conserves both E and p and respects Lorentz invariance. The key idea is that special relativity, which defines E and p , is also associated with uncertainty in x (and also t). In a couple of previous notes, we suggested that this uncertainty in x may be seen by considering:

A rest mass at $x=0$, t transforming to x',t' such that $x'=vt'$ as seen in a frame moving at $-v$ ((6))

This change in x to x' (and t to t') also leads to m_0 transforming to E and p . Furthermore, it is linked to a physical interaction $dp/dt = F$ (where p is given in ((2))).

We suggest that if there is some uncertainty in x as p and E are being created then one should assign an uncertainty to E and p strikes in t and p . This leads to the notion of a probability. We suggest that:

The notion of Newtonian force $dp/dt = F$ and relative reference frames may now be temporarily ignored and one may argue that if a probability is linked with an E , p (for strikes in t and p), then an interaction is represented by multiplying this probability by another. The result must conserve momentum and energy and respect special relativity. This leads to:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is a dynamic skewed probability because $\exp(ipx) \neq \exp(-ipx)$. ((7))

$\exp(ipx)$ shows probabilities for interactions (impulse hits) to occur at x and so should be used to calculate average p and $pp/2m$ because p and $pp/2m$ exist at the point at which an interaction hit occurs. This may lead to a complex average p and $pp/2m$. In a single particle bound state, one avoids this by considering $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ together so that $KE_{ave}(x)$ is real

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \left\{ \sum_p a(p) p p/2m \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((8))$$

We thus try to consider some cases in which a complex average appears and seems to be useful.

$$W(x) = \sum_{p \geq 0} a(p) \exp(ipx)$$

It is possible to create a $W(x)$ using only positive p . This has been done in the literature many times. The Schrodinger equation indicates that

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W + V(x) = E \quad ((9))$$

If $W(x)=0$, then if $E-V(x) \neq 0$ at this x , $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} = 0$ at this x . ((10))

$W(x)$, however, is real. We seek to see if this condition may still hold for $p > 0$ $W(x)$'s.

We consider that simple case of

$$W(x) = \exp(ip_1x) + a \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((11))$$

$$\langle p \rangle = \frac{\int p_1 \exp(ip_1x) + a p_2 \exp(ip_2x)}{W}$$

$$W(x)=0 \text{ for } W^*(x)W(x)=0 \text{ or } 1 + a \cos((p_1-p_2)x) = 0$$

For the special case of $a=1$

$$\langle p \rangle = \frac{1}{(W^*W)} \{ p_1 + p_2 a a + a p_1 \exp(i(p_1-p_2)x) + a p_2 \exp(-i(p_1-p_2)x) \} \quad ((12))$$

For $W(x)=0$, $\cos((p_1-p_2)x) = -1$ and $\sin((p_1-p_2)x) = 0$ so

One may drop the $i \sin()$ parts of ((12)) at such an x , leaving

$$\langle p \rangle = \frac{1}{(1+\cos((p_1-p_2)x))} (p_1+p_2) (1 + \cos((p_1-p_2)x)) \quad ((13))$$

Thus, $\langle p \rangle$ is not affected by $W(x)=0$.

One Dimensional Reflection Refraction

Even though the Schrodinger equation does not use complex average kinetic energy by combining $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, one may see the full dynamic probability at work in one dimensional reflection refraction at an n_1-n_2 (index of refraction) junction. Typically (see (1)), one places the junction at $x=0$ to eliminate the effect of the dynamic probability, but we choose $x \neq 0$ here. We also note that in (1), one applies continuity to $W(x)$ and dW/dx . We argue that one may use physical arguments. (We have mentioned this in a previous note.). $W(x)$ should be continuous because it is a probability, but it is average momentum, a physical quantity, which should also be continuous. The second equation (for a physical point of view) is

$$\{A \exp(ipx) p - p B \exp(-ipx)\} / (A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx)) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2x) / C \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((14))$$

Given that $A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ipx)$ ((15)), ((14)) reduces to the continuity of the derivative.

Using the two equations at $x \neq 0$, we find that

$$C = \frac{2p}{(p+p^2)} \exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) \text{ and } B = \frac{-(p^2-p)}{(p+p^2)} \quad ((16))$$

These results match (1) except that C is multiplied by $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$.

$$\text{This, however, does not change } 1 = B^*(B) + C^*[C] \quad ((17))$$

Thus, one may use the full complex average p in a calculation, we argue.

Conclusion

We argue that it is special relativity which gives rise to both the definitions of E, p and the notion of x being uncertain as it changes from $x=0$ to $x'=vt'$ in an interaction. This leads to the idea of a probability of p hits in x . This allows one to introduce a probability which presumably contains E, p and describes interaction hits in t, x . One may bypass $-Et+px$ (i.e. frames) and $F=dp/dt$ and simply introduce a probability which conserves E, p in an interaction (characterized by $\text{prob}(E_1, p_1) * \text{prob}(E_2, p_2)$, i.e. an AND situation). This leads to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This is a skewed dynamic probability which leads to complex averages such as $\langle p \rangle = \frac{\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)p \exp(ipx)\}}{\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)\}}$ etc. We show that even for $p > 0$ one may have average values which are finite even when $W(x)=0$ and also that there are physical cases in which one may use such a complex average, i.e. one dimensional reflection-refraction.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change